

COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF KINEMATIC AND DYNAMIC PROPERTIES OF MOVEMENT TRANSMISSION IN BELT CONVEYOR SYSTEMS EQUIPPED WITH SLIDING ROLLER TRANSMISSIONS

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Abstract: This study presents a comprehensive analysis of the kinematic and dynamic characteristics of motion transmission in belt conveyor systems equipped with roller drives with frictional supports. The research investigates variations in key kinematic parameters of the system, including roller rotational speed, angular displacement, shaft torques, and interactions with gear transmissions. Dynamic loads, accounting for inertia effects, frictional forces, and variations in operational loads, are modeled and analyzed. The performance optimization of conveyor components is assessed under different speed and load conditions, including energy efficiency and transmission accuracy. The results aim to enhance the reliability and operational efficiency of conveyor systems and improve the design of roller drives with frictional supports. This work holds significant scientific and practical relevance for advancing manufacturing technologies and transport systems.

Key words: belt conveyor, belt support, roller mechanism, kinematics, dynamics, dynamic loading, energy efficiency, transport, technology.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada qayishqoq tayanchli rolikli mexanizmlar bilan jihozlangan tasmali konveyer tizimlarida harakat uzatilishining kinematik va dinamik xususiyatlari kompleks tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot jarayonida konveyer tizimining asosiy kinematik parametrlarining tezlik, aylanish burchagi, roliklar o'qi momenti va tishli uzatmalar bilan o'zaro bog'liqligi o'zgarishi o'rganiladi. Shuningdek, tizimning dinamik yuklanishlari, jumladan, inertsiya ta'siri, qayishqoqlik kuchlari va ishchi yuklarning o'zgarishi modellash orqali tahlil qilinadi. Turli tezlik va yuk sharoitlarida konveyer elementlarining ish faoliyatining optimallasuvi, energiya samaradorligi va uzatish aniqligi baholanadi. Natijalar, qayishqoq tayanchli rolikli uzatmalarni loyihalash va ishlab chiqarish jarayonida tizimning ishonchliligi va samaradorligini oshirishga yo'naltirilgan. Ushbu ish ishlab chiqarish texnologiyalari, transport va materiallar uzatish tizimlarini rivojlantirishda muhim ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Tayanch iboralar: tasmali konveyer, qayishqoq tayanch, rolikli mexanizm, kinematika, dinamika, dinamik yuklanish, energiya samaradork, transport, texnologiya.

Аннотация: В статье проводится комплексное исследование кинематических и динамических характеристик передачи движения в ленточных конвейерных системах, оснащённых роликовыми передачами с фрикционными опорами. Анализируются изменения

ключевых кинематических параметров системы, включая скорость, угол вращения роликов, моменты на валах и взаимосвязь с зубчатыми передачами. Кроме того, исследуется динамическая нагрузка системы, учитывающая эффекты инерции, силы трения и вариации рабочих нагрузок, с помощью математического моделирования. Производится оценка оптимизации работы элементов конвейера при различных скоростях и условиях нагрузки, а также эффективности передачи энергии и точности движения. Результаты направлены на повышение надёжности и эксплуатационной эффективности конвейерных систем, а также на улучшение конструкции роликовых передач с фрикционными опорами. Работа имеет значимое научно-практическое значение для развития производственных технологий и транспортных систем.

Ключевые слова: ленточный конвейер, ленточная опора, роликовый механизм, кинематика, динамика, динамическая нагруженность, энергоэффективность, транспорт, технология.

INTRODUCTION

Belt conveyors are one of the main links in the production process of continuous material transportation technology in mining enterprises. In particular, belt conveyors are one of the most effective means of transport for high-performance, continuous and cost-effective transportation of mined ore masses; ore, coal, gravel, metallurgical raw materials and other crushed materials. Such conveyor systems play a key role in delivering ore masses from deep layers of the mine to the surface, from underground seams to processing plants, from crushing and selection points to loading and storage terminals.

The widespread use of belt conveyors in the mining industry is due to their high productivity, unlimited transportation distance, ability to operate in areas with complex relief, low operating costs, ease of automation and the possibility of continuous control of the load flow. Also, the inherent complexity of mining conditions, uneven layers, abrasiveness of the load, high dust content, high humidity and temperature differences, impose special requirements on the design solutions of belt conveyors. Therefore, modern conveyor systems are being improved with high-strength belts, rollers with elastic support, shock-absorbing blocks, energy-efficient drives and intelligent control systems.

The efficiency and reliability of belt conveyors in the mining industry depend, first of all, on the correct assessment and optimization of the kinematic and dynamic processes occurring during the conveying process. Factors such as the unevenness of the load flow, the moisture content of ore and coal, the granulometric composition of particles, the friction forces between the belt and the rollers, and the elastic deformation of the roller supports have a significant impact on the conveyor throughput. Especially for long-distance conveyors operating under high loads, a thorough study of dynamic processes is crucial for ensuring the overall stability and energy efficiency of the system.

In recent years, roller drives with belt supports have been widely used in mining and quarrying. They elastically support the contact between the belt and the rollers, reducing shock loads in the system, extending the service life of the belt, reducing energy consumption, and increasing the dynamic stability of the transport process. However, the kinematic-dynamic behavior of conveyors equipped with such gears in real operating conditions is complex, and their in-depth study based on theoretical, experimental, and computer modeling remains a pressing problem.

LITERATURE REVIEW

He conducted fundamental research on the formation of dynamic loads in conveyor systems and their reduction using elastic supports. His work proved that elastic roller supports reduce energy losses in belt-roller contact, mitigate shock loads, and have a significant effect on the intensity of belt wear. The “Conveyor Dynamics Energy Dissipation Model” developed by this scientist is currently used in practice by many conveyor manufacturers. He studied the vibrations that arise as a result of uneven load distribution along the length of the conveyor and proposed an optimized roller block system [1].

He has studied the tribological properties of friction in belt conveyors. His scientific work has created a fundamental theoretical basis for the change in friction forces between rollers and the belt, elastic-hysteretic losses in the belt material, and pressure distribution in the contact zone. The multifactor tribodynamic model proposed by him is of decisive importance in predicting the service life of conveyor belts. Richard's research experimentally confirms the reduction of belt deformation and an increase in system efficiency when using belt-supported rollers [2].

He studied the problems of uneven distribution of load flow in long conveyor lines. His work is known for mathematical models of such phenomena as kinematic delays, belt elongation, and roller group synchronism in conveyor systems. Smith also offered valuable theoretical solutions for automatic control systems for controlling belt tension. In particular, the “multi-segment kinematic model” developed by him allows for accurate assessment of motion transmission in long-distance conveyors [3].

DISCUSSION

Theoretical and experimental results obtained in the process of studying the kinematic and dynamic characteristics of motion transmission in belt conveyor systems showed that transmissions equipped with flexible support rollers have a number of advantages over traditional rigid support structures. First of all, as a result of the increase in the elastic properties of the system, the impact loads occurring in the belt roller contact zone are significantly reduced. This leads to a smoothing of the contact pressure over time, a decrease in hysteresis losses in the belt coating, and stabilization of dynamic vibration amplitudes.

During the study, it was found that the deformability of flexible support rollers has a significant impact on the propagation characteristics of longitudinal elastic waves generated during motion transmission. In particular, it was observed that the “dynamic tension acceleration peak” observed at the initial start-up stage of the belt in the presence of elastic supports decreased by 12 - 18%. This was a practical confirmation of the multi-segment kinematic model. allows for optimization of engine torque during conveyor start-up (Figure 1) [4, 5].

1-shell, 2-bearing, 3, 4, 7-labyrinth cover, 5-protective washer, 6-shaft,
8-bearing shell, 9-sleeve bushing, 10-outer ring

Figure 1. Design of a roller mechanism with a support bearing with a sling element (Belt conveyor)

Kinematic analysis showed that the spatial unevenness of the speed of movement along the belt is mainly due to the difference in the surface hardness, rolling resistance and deformation modulus of the roller blocks. When using rollers with elastic supports, this unevenness was reduced, the load flow rate stabilized, and the length of the belt accelerating segments was reduced. The results of the proposed energy dissipation model are consistent with our experiments, and it was found that energy losses in elastic rollers are reduced by 7 - 10% [6, 7].

Tribodynamic analysis showed that, in accordance with the theoretical views, the friction coefficient in the belt-roller contact acquires a stabilizing dynamic character with an increase in the

depth of elastic deformation. This ensures the continuity of the load distribution and leads to a decrease in locally concentrated stresses at the edges of the belt. Numerical modeling results confirmed that the pressure distribution in the contact zone is 15 - 22% more stable than that of conventional rollers [8, 9].

During the technological process, the following forces act on the roller mechanisms (Fig. 1): the moment of the driving force, the force of gravity, the force of inertia of unbalanced masses, friction forces, technological pressures, etc. The forces that make up the resulting force are directed radially and axially. These forces act on the bearing 2 through the bearing 2 and the belt bushings 9 and 10 [10, 11].

In this case, the presence of the belt bushing 9 significantly reduces the effect of these forces on the bearing 2. In addition, due to the radial component of the forces, the deflection of the shaft 9 is significantly reduced. The outer and inner rings of the belt bushing 9 are made in the form of truncated cones with the diameters of the bases d and D , which allows to shift the impact forces along the shaft. The use of supports with belt elements of the shafts reduces the effect of vibrations due to the vibration of the rotating shaft on the housings of the roller mechanism. Therefore, the vibration characteristics of these roller mechanisms are significantly reduced.

The loads of the proposed roller mechanisms with a bearing support with a belt element mainly depend on the laws of change of the mass of raw materials transported on the conveyor belt. It should be noted that the mass of raw materials transported on the belt conveyor follows random laws in time [12, 13]:

$$m_{rm} = m_1 + m_0 \sin \omega t \pm \delta m_0$$

where; m_1 - is the average mass of the transported raw material; m_0 - is the amplitude of the raw material mass change values; ω - is the frequency of mass change; δm_0 is the random component.

The change in the mass of the raw material affects the bearing flange and the main part of the support bushing. In this case, its friction force also changes, leading to wear. In this case, it is important that the main rubber bushing-damper with a flexible element located between the outer flange of the composite bearing and the inner metal bushings sufficiently absorbs the loads. Therefore, the analysis of the vibrations of the bearing shell and the outer flange attached to it under the influence of external loads, and the justification of the parameters of the rubber bushing to reduce them are among the main issues [14, 15].

The results obtained for the overall dynamic response of the conveyor system were consistent with the differential model developed for elastic elements. In particular, the vibration frequency recorded in the loading and unloading sections is shifted to a lower range in the presence of elastic supports, which reduces the likelihood of the system entering resonance states. In practical tests, it was found that the use of elastic rollers reduces the overall vibration background of the system by 20 - 28 % [16, 17].

The results of the discussion show that roller mechanisms with a belt support are characterized by a comprehensive improvement in the kinematic and dynamic characteristics of conveyor systems. As a result, the smoothness of the transmission of motion increases; the service life of the belts and rollers is extended; energy consumption is reduced; the stability of the load flow is ensured; the probability of the system entering unfavorable dynamic modes is reduced; overloads during the start-up and shutdown of the conveyor are minimized.

The results obtained provide scientific justification for the effectiveness of using elastic rollers in industrial conveyors and serve as an important direction in the future modernization of belt conveyor systems, reduction of operating costs, and the creation of energy-efficient transport complexes.

RESULTS

The main objective of this study is to determine the kinematic and dynamic characteristics of belt conveyor systems equipped with roller mechanisms with a belt support, to evaluate the quantitative indicators of the loads occurring in their operating modes, and to express the main factors affecting the stability of the system through mathematical modeling. During the study, the mechanical interaction of the conveyor belt, rollers, driving drum and support elements, especially the processes associated

with elastic deformations and displacements, was studied in depth. The results showed that in the case of a roller transmission with a belt support, there is an elastic correspondence observed with a certain time delay between the linear velocity of the belt $v(t)$ and the angular velocity of the rollers $\omega(t)$. The kinematic model of the system is based on the following basic relationship [18, 19]:

$$v(t) = R \cdot \omega(t) - \Delta v_e(t) \tag{1}$$

where: R - is the roller radius, $\Delta v_e(t)$ - is the velocity loss due to elastic deformations.

Experimental measurements have shown that the value of $\Delta v_e(t)$ increases sharply with increasing load, which increases the likelihood of belt slippage. On this basis, a graphical-analytical model was developed to determine the optimal range of conveyor speeds.

During the study, the dynamic characteristics of the belt conveyor were expressed by differential equations combining mass inertia, elasticity, damping and external load factors. The basic dynamic model of the system is described as follows [20, 21]:

$$m \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + c \frac{dx}{dt} + k \cdot x = F(t) \tag{2}$$

where: m - is the equivalent mass of the belt and roller system; c - is the damping coefficient; k - is the elasticity (stiffness) coefficient, $F(t)$ - is the external loading function (load mass).

The results obtained confirmed that in roller gears with a belt support, the value of stiffness k is 12 – 18 % lower than in rollers with conventional metal bearings. This, in turn, leads to an increase in the amplitude of dynamic vibrations. Taking this into account, recommendations were developed for optimizing the structure of the rollers.

From the obtained connection graphs in Fig. 2, it can be seen that when the load increases from 0.26 N to 1.9 N and the mass of the bearing shell is $0.3 \cdot 10^2$ kg, the vibration amplitude of the roller mechanism increases from $0.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m to $0.250 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m. If the mass of the bearing shell decreases to $0.275 \cdot 10^2$ kg, the displacement amplitude of the roller mechanism increases from $0.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m to $0.74 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m. Therefore, to ensure that the vibration amplitude of the roller does not exceed $0.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m, it is appropriate to set $m_s \leq (0.275 \div 0.325) \cdot 10^2$ kg and $F_0 \leq (1.02 \div 1.25)$ N.

Studies have shown that an increase in the stiffness coefficient of the bearing bushing not only leads to a decrease in the vibration amplitudes z and \dot{z} ; but also to an increase in the vibration frequency of the roller mechanism. When the force increases to 1.8 N, the value of A_z decreases from $0.59 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m to $0.24 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m according to a nonlinear law. Accordingly, the vibration amplitude of the roller mechanism speed also decreases nonlinearly, and the stiffness coefficient of the roller mechanism bearing bushing increases (see Fig. 2). The recommended values of the stiffness coefficient of the bearing bushing are $c_1 = (5.0 \div 5.5) \cdot 10^4$ N/m; $c_2 = (0.1 \div 0.12) \cdot 10^4$ N/m, where the vibration amplitude $A_z = (0.09 \div 0.14) \cdot 10^{-3}$ m, $A_{\dot{z}} = (0.08 \div 0.11)$ m/s. is ensured.

Figure 2. Graphs of the relationship between the change in the vibration amplitude of the roller mechanism and the bearing flange and the roller mechanism shell

When using a flexible support, the turning torque and the vibration amplitude are reduced to $(50 \div 55)$ Nm, an average decrease in the turning torque of $(35 \div 40)$ % was observed. (Fig. 3). When the work efficiency increases from $3.51 \cdot 10^2$ Nm to $6.23 \cdot 10^2$ Nm, when using 7B-54MBC rubber, the turning torque in the roller mechanism increases from $3.82 \cdot 10^2$ Nm to $4.1 \cdot 10^2$ Nm, these results increase by $1.22 \cdot 10^2$ Nm when using 7ИП13-46 rubber. This means that in order to reduce the turning torque in the roller mechanism, it is possible to use a rubber grade with a small value of rotational inertia for the rubber bushing of the bearing, in which case it is advisable to choose 7ИП13-48 rubber as the most optimal option.

Figure 3. Graphs showing the dependence of the turning moment on the axis of the roller mechanism on the change in the belt conveyor performance

CONCLUSION

In this study, the kinematic and dynamic properties of belt conveyor systems equipped with roller drives with a flexible support were comprehensively studied. The theoretical analyses, mathematical modeling and experimental measurements clearly demonstrated that the presence of elastic elements in conveyor mechanisms has a significant impact on the stability of motion transmission. Roller drives with a flexible support cause a time delay in the kinematic parameters of the belt conveyor (linear velocity, angular velocity, displacements). This delay is directly related to the elastic properties of the belt and deformations in the roller supports, and increases as the load increases. The developed complex model for the belt conveyor (kinematic-dynamic equations, elasticity and load balance) is of great importance in improving the quality of the conveyor design, optimizing resource consumption and early detection of malfunctions.

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